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Introduction of Independent Education in Foreign Language Classes and its Challenges*

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ABSTRACT

It is a type of intellectual, spiritual activity that aims to form knowledge about society, nature, and oneself, and is a too multiracial, complex, controversial process. An individual cannot succeed in any task without awareness and comprehension of the environment around us. However, he succeeds if, through his invention, he enriches all. In turn, this is an independent training that takes people of all ages to the peak of maturity. An individual will be more apt to learn the problems and overcome them.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the quality not just of primary schools but also of middle schools, the birthplace of our country's fundamental skills, such that their curriculum is up-to-date, lifts it to global levels and contributes by international languages to the world's culture. There are broader circumstances and better chances to present the world more thoroughly and truthfully and share both our successes and best deeds since independence. The exponential proliferation of data flows, developments in research and technological growth, news, expanded accessibility for international languages, and knowledge and communication technologies are all accessible only in the classroom as part of the globalization phase. We also realize now that the key answer to this issue is private schooling. Individual schooling. The level of information, skills, and skills that students need to improve in education and education is therefore essential to focus on.

Independent learning is associated closely with self-reliance. Independent thought is a mental process in which a person identifies his objectives and priorities, depending on his / her understanding and experience of existence and manages it individually, utilizing different ways, processes, and tools, in his intellectual ability. The independent study's primary aim is to train the pupil in a certain amount of skills to carry out the job under the teacher's direct or indirect supervision. The potential to function critically produces autonomous practice. It is essential to empower self-employed young people in

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their autonomous vision of an independent society. There are a rising urge and willingness to learn foreign languages, particularly in the 21st century, the age of learning. The instructor, makes the students keen on what is being taught. Consequently, a student's progress in an EFL program is enhanced significantly. Harun Rashid, at all, (2020). Extensive and efficient usage of all areas of the life of digital information technology calls for and professionals' capacity to do autonomous work. The new training is also necessary to be a testimony to the development and application of an autonomous education framework in higher schools and the introduction of a legal structure for learning student knowledge and skills to functional independence.

Therefore, more focus must be given to enhancing the quality of preparing prospective foreign language teachers for technical skills. Some factors can positively influence this performance, including:

1. The continuing theoretical and science teaching to plan, execute, and monitor independent student learning for higher education teachers;
2. Improving the educational information framework for pupils, their talents, and their autonomous learning capabilities;
3. Scientific and methodical seminars association, professional school company training programs, the transmission of best practices;
4. Using revolutionary technology to boost adult education quality;
5. In terms of the diversity of technological methods and innovations utilized in the instructional method, the teaching standard is excellent or adequate, depending on the type and distribution methods. It is worth pointing out that a "Private Student Job Organisation" policy has been established by the Uzbek Republic's Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. The "Model Rules for Students' Organization, Supervision and Assay" policy was implemented under the order. The bureaucratic, quality management decides the order, and performance monitoring of students in compliance with the Decree of the cabinet of ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of 16 August 2001 No 343 "On recognition of state higher education requirements."
6. A self-learning person may realize what he or she has experienced and can do it. However, he or she can still be psychologically handicapped and can unintentionally alter life's habits. It is also necessary to know how and how individual schooling is to be given. This is because today's students are not educated. After all, the way they are specifically trained and are inadequate for the future, society is inadequate, and they need to improve their knowledge.

Be serious about handling it in the best direction. The new world of the 21st century and the empirical knowledge of our students is quickly redundant. Therefore, we must pay careful attention to the student's academic performance during their whole education to encourage him to acquire experience and knowledge to potential independently. Academic success is measured not only by learning elements but also by successful aspects. Fear is a negative emotion that can help you learn to be effective, Harun Rashid, (2020). The pupil's academic work is a significant part of the educational process and is demonstrated in the program for a particular subject. One-third of the hours expended on one subject of DTS, curricula, and model programs are dedicated to independent study analyses. However, the procedures for allocating independent hours of study, the standard of independent analysis, and their techniques at the required level could not be checked and identified. We are aware that the author, the instructor, and the pupil, and the foreign language, which is the focus of the research, is one of the critical challenges of Ling Vododidaktik. Independent studies in a foreign language may take two forms: the student's independent work, which is specified in a program for learning a specific topic, is an integral part of the education work. Academic research is given for a third of the number of hours allotted to a single topic under the State Curriculum Policy, curricula, and sample programs. The allocation of independent research hours, however,

The research study's quality and the organization's methods were not investigated and implemented at the necessary stage. The interaction between the tutor, the student, and the other language, which is the focus of research, is regarded as one of the primary tasks of the LIGVODIDATIC. The independent

study of the language of a foreign country will take two forms: human studying a foreign language with the assistance of various teaching instruments (textbooks, electronic textbooks, guides, computer systems, T.V., and Video programs),-self-study and self-study;

For both students and instructors, this is a particular method of instruction. We want to learn. We want to dream. For independent study, a range of issues need to be answered, including material, nature of self-employed teaching activities under the direct direction of the instructor-the intent, material, nature, controls of self-employed function outside the classroom (home, library, study, reading space, etc.) under direct or indirect supervision. Direct or indirect supervision. It is highly necessary to function individually in the learning of foreign languages, for without the individual actions, mastery of every industry is not total. Sources indicate that independent educational theory (Gulomov A, Rozikov O, Nurullaeva Sh, etc.) is partly studied in the wider educational sector.

CONCLUSION

N.E. Pavlov sees individual students' study as a core part of the schooling phase in his empirical essay on independent student study and examines the students' development of thinking abilities, abilities, and knowledge. In this document, the author believes that new teaching aids and purely hierarchical methodologies must be established to coordinate and draw students through the individual educational phase. Naturally, no adult study may be an abandoned operation, explicitly or implicitly regulated or unregulated. Owing to the rapid production of I.T. and its extensive usage in the educational sector, the need for individual study is on the rise in the 21st century. Experts from here and internationally concentrate on self-employed schooling, which demonstrates the value of the independent study.

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